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Title: SOP to flush the inlet components (infusion line and needle insert placed in ESI spray insert) prior to and after calibration of Orbitrap Exploris 480 equipped with OptaMax Ion source.

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Prior to each removal or reinstallation, always wear a new pair of lint- and powder-free gloves.

Make a note about flushing the inlet components to the Logbook.

SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific for SII Xcalibur 1.7.0.468, Orbitrap Exploris Tune 4.3.458.15

To remove syringe from the holder

1. Turn Off the flow from the syringe pump using *Syringe OFF* icon in Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application.
2. In the Tune window (Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application), place the MS to Standby Mode.
3. Remove the syringe from the syringe pump holder as follows:
 - a) Lift the syringe holder off of the syringe.
 - b) Press the pusher block's release button and slide the block to the left.
 - c) Remove the syringe from the holder.
 - d) Carefully remove the syringe needle from the Teflon tube on the syringe adapter assembly.

To install the ESI spray insert with the calibration needle insert

1. In the Tune window, place the MS to Off Mode (Figure 1). After the API source cools to room temperature (about 20 mins) you can start to remove the currently installed H-ESI spray insert.

Figure 1 Power mode icons showing the selected mode

- a) **For acquisition**, the H-ESI spray insert with **black nut** is equipped with hi-flow needle, **HESI Hi Flow Needle Insert 100 um ID32G (OPTON-30694)** and **red PEEK tubing** connecting the grounding union and the needle insert's nozzle union.
 - b) **For calibration**, the **ESI spray insert** with **beige nut** must be equipped with 'L' marked low-flow needle, **HESI LoFlo Needle Insert 50 um ID35G (OPTON-30139)** and **beige PEEK tubing (PN 80000-22032)** connecting the grounding union and the needle insert's nozzle union.
2. Disconnect the red tubing of nozzle union (square PEEK ferrule). Unscrew the black nut of the current H-ESI spray insert, carefully remove it out of the API housing and store it in the Spray Insert Holder.
 3. Pin-oriented place the ESI spray insert with calibration 'L' needle into the API housing, screw it by the black nut and replace the red PEEK tubing by the beige one connecting the grounding union and the needle insert's nozzle union.
 4. In the Tune window, place the MS to Standby Mode and wait till the ion transfer tube temperature increases to 325°C.

To flush the inlet components

1. From the grounding union, unscrew the ferule connecting the divert valve and replace it via ferule connected through the infusion line to the syringe's needle (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Flushing the inlet components prior to and after calibration

2. Since **Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution (A39239)** is used for calibration, rinse the syringe with 50:50 acetonitrile/water solution at least five times.
3. Flush the infusion line and the calibration needle insert placed in the H-ESI spray insert at least once:
 - a) Load a 500 μl cleaned syringe with 50:50 acetonitrile/water solution.
 - b) Carefully reinsert the syringe needle into the Teflon tube.
 - c) Place the H-ESI spray insert to position 3 of the API housing to assure that flushing solution is leading into the waste tube.
 - d) In the Tune window, via *Syringe ON* icon turn on flow and change it 3 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ \rightarrow 45 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. Prior to flushing volume runs out, change flow 45 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ \rightarrow 3 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ and by *Syringe OFF* icon turn it Off, Check that tubing connections do not leak during flushing procedure.
 - e) Following flushing, adjust the H-ESI spray insert to position 1 of the API housing.
4. The inlet components are now ready to calibrate the MS according to Calibration the MS procedure.
5. After successful calibration of the MS, flush the infusion line and the calibration needle insert in the same way as described.

To replace the calibration/acquisition needle insert by the new one to the ESI/H-ESI spray insert

1. Check the MS is placed in Standby Mode and disconnect the tubing out of the beige nozzle union of the current needle insert.
2. Carefully replace the current needle insert with the new one as follows (see Figures 3-4):
 - a) With one hand, twist the locking nut and pull the collar with pins straight out
 - b) Loosen the needle insert's nozzle union (square PEEK ferrule) and slowly pull it out of the spray insert.

Figure 3 Removing the needle insert out of the spray insert

- c) Place the new needle insert into spray insert and secure it by rotating square PEEK ferrule about four turns.
- d) To **Needle Adjustment Tool (PN80000-20957)**, place the spray insert and check it is seated firmly.
- e) By rotating the square PEEK ferrule, adjust new needle insert protruding the Tool to align its tip end with the edge of the Tool. The needle insert protrudes within 1.2 to 1.5 mm specification.

Figure 4 Adjusting the needle insert position by the Tool

- f) Place the collar with pins over, screw the locking nut over the spray insert and place it into the API housing and reconnect the tubing.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Exploris Series: Operating Manual and OptaMax NG: Ion source user guide (Thermo Fisher Scientific).